

**EFFECT OF FODDER BEET ON THE AGROCHEMICAL INDICATORS
OF SOIL**

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**ВЛИЯНИЕ КОРМОВОЙ СВЕКЛЫ НА АГРОХИМИЧЕСКИЕ
ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ПОЧВЫ**

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Abstract. *All soil properties, including agronomic, ecological, biochemical, and physical characteristics, are directly or indirectly influenced by soil density, i.e., bulk mass. For all soil types, the optimal density in the plow layer (0-30 cm) is considered to be 1.20-1.22 g/cm³. In this study, it was found that the amount of humus in the soil where fodder beet was cultivated decreased from 0.003% to 0.010%, while the total nitrogen content decreased by 0.005-0.011%, 0.008-0.015%, and 0.011-0.018%, respectively, depending on the experimental conditions.*

Keywords: *Fodder beet, total nitrogen content, soil fertility, typical gray soils.*

Annotatsiya. *Tuproqning barcha xossalari, jumladan, agrotexnik, ekologik, biokimyoviy va fizik xususiyatlariga bevosita yoki bilvosita tuproq zichligi, ya'ni*

massa massasi ta'sir qiladi. Barcha tuproq turlari uchun shudgor qatlamidagi optimal zichlik (0-30 sm) 1,20-1,22 g/sm³ deb hisoblanadi. Ushbu tadqiqotda em-xashak lavlagi yetishtirilgan tuproqdagi chirindi miqdori tajriba sharoitiga qarab 0,003% dan 0,010% gacha kamayganligi, umumiy azot miqdori esa mos ravishda 0,005-0,011%, 0,008-0,015% va 0,018-0,01% ga kamayganligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Yem-xashak lavlagi, umumiy azot miqdori, tuproq unumdorligi, tipik bo'z tuproqlar.*

Аннотация. *Все свойства почвы, включая агрономические, экологические, биохимические и физические характеристики, напрямую или косвенно зависят от плотности почвы, т. е. объемной массы. Для всех типов почв оптимальной плотностью в пахотном слое (0-30 см) считается 1,20-1,22 г/см³. В ходе данного исследования было установлено, что количество гумуса в почве, где выращивалась кормовая свекла, уменьшилось с 0,003% до 0,010%, а общее содержание азота уменьшилось на 0,005-0,011%, 0,008-0,015% и 0,011-0,018% соответственно в зависимости от условий эксперимента.*

Ключевые слова: *Кормовая свекла, общее содержание азота, плодородие почвы, типичные серые почвы.*

Introduction.

Soil and its fertile layer are among the key biological factors affecting plant life. The amount of nutrients in the soil directly influences plant growth, development, yield, and quality, as noted in numerous scientific sources.

The research on fodder beet was conducted in the typical gray soils of Samarkand region, characterized by a low nutrient content. This observation was confirmed by an agrochemical analysis of soil samples taken before the start of the experiment [4].

Fodder beet is a juicy, easily digestible, and nutritious type of fodder. It contains essential nutrients required by livestock, including carbohydrates, nitrogen-free extractive substances, mineral salts, and vitamins.

Depending on the variety, fodder beet contains 85–90% water and is rich in enzymes. It helps improve the digestion of coarse fodder in the digestive system of livestock.

1 kg of fodder beet root contains 0.11–0.12 feed units. The semi-sweet crown part contains 0.14–0.16 feed units, and the leaves contain 0.10–0.12 feed units. The dietary ratio of fodder beet roots is considered higher than that of sugar beet. The ratio of extractive to nitrogen-free substances is 1:5.1 in fodder beet, while in sugar beet it is 1:7.7.

Fodder beet, like sugar beet, originated in the 18th–19th centuries and was initially cultivated for food, later for sugar production and fodder purposes.

This crop is widely grown in European countries such as the United Kingdom, France, Belgium, Germany, and Denmark, where dairy and cattle farming are well-developed. Although the cultivated area of fodder beet has decreased in recent years due to the labor-intensive nature of its farming, its yield per hectare has significantly increased. In these countries, fodder beet yields reach 600–900 centners per hectare.

Research Methodology

According to 2023 data on the initial agrochemical state of the soil, the humus content in the plow layer (0-30 cm) was 0.918%, and in the subsoil layer (30-50 cm), it was 0.871%. The total nitrogen content in these layers was 0.090% and 0.063%, respectively, while phosphorus content was 0.168% and 0.142%, and potassium content was 1.514% and 1.139%. The levels of mobile nutrients in the 0-30 cm layer were as follows: nitrate nitrogen – 10.1 mg/kg (very low), mobile phosphorus – 25.1 mg/kg (low), and exchangeable potassium – 220 mg/kg (moderate). According to soil nutrient classification, this indicates very low nitrogen, low phosphorus, and moderate potassium content [2,5].

In experimental variants with a planting density of 70-80 thousand plants per hectare (variants 1, 2, 3, 4), humus content decreased by 0.003% to 0.010%. In variants with 90-100 thousand plants per hectare (variants 5, 6, 7, 8), it decreased by 0.003% to 0.013%, while in variants with 110-120 thousand plants per hectare (variants 9, 10, 11, 12), it decreased by 0.008% to 0.015%. The total nitrogen content also decreased accordingly by 0.005-0.011%, 0.008-0.015%, and 0.011-0.018%. Similar patterns were observed for phosphorus and potassium content.

Analysis and results

The mobile nutrient content also followed this trend, with nitrate nitrogen levels decreasing by 0.1-1.7 mg/kg in variants with a planting density of 70-80 thousand plants per hectare, 0.3-2.0 mg/kg in variants with 90-100 thousand plants per hectare, and 0.6-2.1 mg/kg in variants with 110-120 thousand plants per hectare. Mobile phosphorus content decreased by 0.5-0.9 mg/kg, 1.0-2.2 mg/kg, and 0.6-2.1 mg/kg, respectively.

Data on mobile nutrients indicate that as the mineral fertilizer application rate decreases, the amount of available nutrients in the soil also declines. For instance, in variant 2 (90-100 thousand plants per hectare with NPK 120:90:60 kg/ha), the nitrate nitrogen content decreased by 0.5 mg/kg, while in variant 3 (NPK 160:120:90 kg/ha), it decreased by 0.3 mg/kg, and in variant 4 (NPK 200:140:100 kg/ha), it decreased by 0.1 mg/kg. Similarly, mobile phosphorus content decreased by 0.09 mg/kg, 0.08 mg/kg, and 0.06 mg/kg, respectively

A similar trend was observed in planting densities of 90-100 thousand plants per hectare, where nitrate nitrogen decreased by 0.04%, 0.03%, and 0.03%, while mobile phosphorus content decreased by 1.1 mg/kg, 1.2 mg/kg, and 1.0 mg/kg. In variants with 110-120 thousand plants per hectare, nitrate nitrogen content decreased by 1.2%, 0.08%, and 0.06%, while mobile phosphorus content decreased by 1.3 mg/kg, 1.2 mg/kg, and 1.1 mg/kg.

At the start of the study in 2023, the bulk density of the plow layer was 1.345 g/cm³, while in the subsoil layer, it was 1.407 g/cm³.

Root crops, including fodder beet, tend to compact the plow layer more than other plants. This has been confirmed in numerous scientific studies. As root crops enlarge, soil density increases. Therefore, planting density and mineral fertilizer rates influence soil bulk mass to varying degrees [1].

At the end of the first year of the study (2023), data analysis showed that as fodder beet planting density increased, soil bulk density also increased. In variants with a density of 70-80 thousand plants per hectare, soil bulk density increased by 0.008-0.079 g/cm³; in variants with 90-100 thousand plants per hectare, it increased by 0.022-0.089 g/cm³; and in variants with 110-120 thousand plants per hectare, it increased by 0.025-0.097 g/cm³.

№	Seedling thickness, thousand/ha	Mineral fertilizer standards, kg/ha	At the beginning of the period of action		At the beginning of the period of action	
			0-30	30-50	0-30	30-50
1	70-80	Without fertilizer (control)	1,345	1,407	1,424	1,457
2		NPK 120:90:60			1,387	1,433
3		NPK 160:120:90			1,375	1,430
4		NPK 200:140:100			1,358	1,424
5	90-100	Without fertilizer (control)	1,345	1,407	1,431	1,461
6		NPK 120:90:60			1,392	1,439
7		NPK 160:120:90			1,387	1,432
8		NPK 200:140:100			1,367	1,424
9	110-120	Without fertilizer (control)	1,345	1,407	1,442	1,468

Conclusion

It can be concluded that applying mineral fertilizers at NPK 120:90:60 kg/ha reduces soil humus content by 0.008-0.012%, total nitrogen by 0.006-0.012%, nitrate nitrogen by 0.4-1.2 mg/kg, and mobile phosphorus by 0.9-1.3 mg/kg compared to the initial levels.

Furthermore, increasing the planting density of fodder beet to 110-120 thousand plants per hectare decreases the humus content in the 0-30 cm layer by 0.008-0.012%, total nitrogen by 0.011-0.012%, nitrate nitrogen by 0.6-1.2 mg/kg, and mobile phosphorus by 1.1-1.3 mg/kg. Reducing fertilizer application from NPK 200:140:100 kg/ha to NPK 120:90:60 kg/ha lowers humus content by 0.003-0.005%, total nitrogen by 0.001-0.002%, nitrate nitrogen by 0.2-0.4 mg/kg, and mobile phosphorus by 0.1-0.2 mg/kg.

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